

International Association of
Students in Agricultural and
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FOOD AND AGRICULTURE YOUTH INSTITUTE (FAYI) POLICY DOCUMENT

A One Health Approach for the Prevention of Antimicrobial Resistance in Livestock for Safeguarding both Animal and Public Health in Bangladesh

Position Paper

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❖ We acknowledge that:

- Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) poses a critical threat to public and livestock health, food security, and environmental sustainability all over the world; especially in developing countries like Bangladesh. It results in increased morbidity, mortality, and disease burden, healthcare expenses, and worsened livelihoods.
- By the year 2050, it is predicted that the lack of control over AMR will result in a catastrophic scenario, leading to a staggering number of 300 million fatalities worldwide, coupled with extensive financial losses of 100 trillion US dollars. Moreover, the uncontrolled AMR issue is now expected to cause a significant decline of 11% in the production of livestock^{1, 2}.
- The negative impacts of AMR on livestock will predominantly manifest as reduced efficiency, subsequently resulting in a deterioration of food security. The developing countries exhibit an enhanced susceptibility to AMR due to several factors, including inadequate or excessive use of antibiotics in farm animals, unstandardized pharmaceutical products, ineffective drug policies, inadequate oversight and surveillance of antibiotic usage, and a lack of comprehension and awareness regarding AMR among livestock farmers and so forth.
- In the context of livestock and poultry farming of developing countries, antibiotics are used as growth promoters and prophylactic agents instead of as therapeutic applications³. This misapplication of antibiotics in livestock and poultry conspicuously contributed to the escalating prevalence of AMR. Consequently, thanks to lack of respect of suspension times before entering food production, residues of antimicrobials entered the human diet through the consumption of animal-based foods.
- Additionally, this imprudent and unscrupulous deployment of antibiotics further exacerbates the dissemination of AMR, extending its sphere of influence from animal farming to the broader environment, thereby constituting significant and pervasive public health risks.
- In Bangladesh, the first National Drug Policy was established by the Government in 1982 with the objectives of ensuring the safety, quality, and price control of drugs for the sake of human health⁴. Nonetheless, no comparable policy or guideline exists pertaining to the livestock production sectors. However, in order to restrict the use of antibiotics in animal feeds, the government of Bangladesh enacted a legislation titled the "Bangladesh Fish Feed and Animal Feed Act 2010"⁵. The previous research studies encompass a range of concepts and arguments regarding the beneficial and detrimental aspects of antibiotics in relation to livestock production and disease prevention⁶. However, the lack of strict monitoring on antibiotic sales by the pharmacy shops without prescriptions has made antibiotics easily available to farmers. Moreover, the abundances of unqualified practitioners (Quacks) contributed to the escalation of AMR owing to the inappropriate administration of antibiotics in animals.

❖ **We believe that failure to adequately regulate the appropriate use of antibiotics in livestock production and treatment can lead to:**

- Endangering food security, which can put public health in risk.
- Posing a formidable obstacle in addressing infections that were once controllable within the realms of human and veterinary medicine. Consequently, this may result in increased illnesses, incidence of diseases, and mortality rates.
- Enhancing the cost of healthcare due to the need for more expensive and potentially less effective treatments, long treatment plans and procedures for both humans and animals.
- Complicating the surgical procedures, as post-operative infections will be more challenging to manage. This can result in higher rates of surgical complications, longer recovery times, and post-operative infections for the patients.
- Increasing susceptibility of different infectious diseases among the elders, infants, and individuals with compromised immune systems.
- Re-emergence of various diseases previously which were under control, like tuberculosis and malaria, as major health threats, as existing treatments will be ineffective against resistant strains. It can also allow the outbreak of several epidemics and pandemics, such as Covid-19 which was the recent pandemic across the globe.
- Inclining long-term economic crises due to prolonged illnesses, increased healthcare expenses, and reduced agricultural productivity can lead to reduced GDP and job losses of a country.
- Releasing antibiotic residues into the environment can contribute to the development of environmental AMR. This can affect aquatic ecosystems and wildlife.
- Diminishing trust in both human and veterinary medicine that can assist in reducing adherence to treatment regimens and vaccination programs.

❖ **We call on governments to:**

- Establish more effective and appropriate national policies and strategies to combat AMR.
- Ensure coordinated efforts across ministries for a holistic approach to mitigate AMR.
- Regulate livestock practices regarding proper antibiotic use and develop antibiotic stewardship.

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- Monitor for quack practicing strictly.
- Strengthen the regulatory framework governing the sales and use of antibiotics in both the human and animal sectors.
- Increase educational efforts targeting healthcare providers, veterinarians, and farmers about prudent antibiotic use.
- Encourage the adoption of antibiotic stewardship programs in livestock clinics and hospitals.
- Develop and implement public awareness campaigns to educate the outreach communities about the dangers of AMR and the importance of completing antibiotic courses in animals as prescribed.
- Allocate resources and financial support for research on AMR through the innovation of new antibiotics and alternative treatments.
- Collaborate with other national, international organizations and neighboring countries to address AMR as a regional issue, sharing best practices and resources.
- Engage with pharmaceutical companies, pharmacies, and private healthcare providers to ensure they follow responsible antibiotic use practices.
- Promote transparency and authentic data sharing among stakeholders, including healthcare providers, and pharmaceutical companies, to enable effective monitoring and analysis of antibiotic use.
- Develop and disseminate evidence-based antibiotic prescribing guidelines widely for healthcare professionals to promote responsible antibiotic use.
- Strengthen national reference laboratories and veterinary hospitals for microbiology and antibiotic resistance testing to ensure the development of antibiotic stewardship that will lead to accurate diagnostics and surveillance.
- Invest in infrastructure in veterinary clinics and hospitals to ensure access to quality veterinary services in underserved areas to reduce the risk of infections.
- Strengthen food safety measures to prevent the contamination of food products with antibiotic-resistant bacteria such as ensuring meat hygiene, milk hygiene etc.
- Monitor the sales of antibiotics in pharmacy shops strictly to ensure proper distribution of the drugs to the farmers according to prescriptions.

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- Evaluate and update policies and interventions to align with the evolving landscape of AMR on a regular basis.
- Motivate and support youths to combat AMR issues through increasing public awareness.

❖ **We call on national pharmaceutical companies to:**

- Apply responsible manufacturing practices that prioritize quality and safety in antibiotic production. National pharmaceutical companies should comply with international quality standards and Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) to minimize the potential for antibiotic contamination.
- Reduce the production of antibiotics that are considered of low clinical importance or have high resistance potential.
- Increase the production of antibiotics that are critically needed.
- Enhance the funding supports for research and development of new antibiotics as well as alternative treatments to counter the challenge of AMR.
- Encourage transparency and data sharing within the pharmaceutical industries to monitor and analyze antibiotic qualities.
- Contribute to public awareness campaigns aimed at educating the outreach communities about the responsible use of antibiotics.
- Collaborate with researchers and scientists to contribute to the body of knowledge on AMR.

❖ **We call on farmers to:**

- Use antibiotics in a responsible and judicious manner in livestock farming and treatment. The farmers should strictly follow veterinary guidelines and only use antibiotics when necessary to treat diagnosed infections.
- Consult with registered veterinarians regularly for proper diagnosis and prescription of antibiotics for treatments. Farmers should not administer antibiotics without veterinary guidance.
- Avoid the quacks for appropriate use of antibiotics in the animals.

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- Focus on disease prevention through improved animal husbandry practices, hygiene, and vaccination that will assist in reducing the need for antibiotics.
- Participate in training and educational programs on antibiotic stewardship, focusing on the importance of responsible antibiotic use and its impact on public health that are provided by the governments, national and international institutions.

❖ **We call on veterinarians to:**

- Use of antibiotics in a judicious and responsible way. The antibiotics should be prescribed after ensuring bacterial infections through clinical evidence and selected with the narrowest spectrum of activity.
- Participate in different educational programs and training for the best practices for responsible antibiotic use.
- Develop and implement antibiotic stewardship programs to ensure the proper prescription of antibiotics.
- Communicate with the clients effectively, ensuring that clients understand the importance of following prescribed treatments, including proper dosage and duration.
- Educate clients in the food production industry about responsible antibiotic use, including adhering to withdrawal periods for food safety.
- Participate actively in research and innovations related to AMR, such as exploring alternative and effective treatments, epidemiological study of diseases, and diagnostic methods.
- Participate in the development of national and regional policies and guidelines related to AMR and to advocate for their implementation.
- Educate outreach communities regarding proper antibiotic use in animals and advice on proper disposal and management practices.
- Contribute to AMR surveillance efforts by sharing data on antibiotic use, resistance patterns, and animal health.
- Facilitate partnerships between veterinary associations, students associations and other organizations working to combat AMR, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration.
- Engaging with local communities to raise awareness about the responsible use of antibiotics in veterinary medicine and promote AMR education.

❖ We call on academicians to:

- Conduct in-depth studies on various aspects of AMR, including resistance mechanisms, prevalence, distribution, and the impact on public health.
- Generate high-quality data to inform evidence-based policies and interventions.
- Carry out research on the development of new antibiotics and alternative treatments such as phage therapy, probiotics, immunotherapies and others to counteract AMR.
- Collaborate with the different educational institutions and veterinary professionals to design and evaluate antibiotic stewardship programs.
- Evaluate existing national and international policies related to AMR and provide the best policy recommendations based on research findings to support more effective policy development and implementation.
- Conduct interdisciplinary research that incorporates perspectives from health sciences, social sciences, environmental sciences, and agriculture to address AMR as a One Health issue.
- Foster international collaboration in research by participating in global research networks, sharing data and findings, and contributing to a global understanding of AMR.
- Conduct studies on genome and environmental factors to understand the genetic and non-genetic basis of resistance in pathogens and track the spread of resistant strains.
- Publish research findings in reputable scientific journals and engage in knowledge dissemination through conferences, workshops, and policy briefs.
- Advocate for increasing funding support for conducting AMR research from government agencies, philanthropic organizations, and international partners.

❖ We call on UN bodies, Veterinary Institutions, Public Health Institutions, Medical Societies and other associated institutions to:

- Promote One Health collaborations among international organizations, member countries in order to determine the underlying causations for increasing the prevalence of AMR in a particular geography or country in order to develop or suggest effective policies for the AMR mitigation.

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- Collaborate with national government and local institutions to support the development and implementation of national action plans and strategies to combat AMR.
- Enhance financial support for conducting studies, increasing resources, carrying out public awareness campaigns, educating local farmers and outreach communities about the responsible use of antibiotics, the dangers of AMR, and the importance of completing antibiotic courses in animals as prescribed.
- Advocate for a multi-sectoral approach that include agriculture, health, and environment sectors to address AMR comprehensively through One Health approach.

❖ **We call on civil societies and local people to:**

- Participate in different workshops and seminars to gather knowledge and disseminate the knowledge among the neighboring people and livestock farmers, which will enhance the public awareness regarding AMR and its effects due to misuse of antibiotics in livestock and public health.

❖ **We call on regulatory and oversight bodies to:**

- Monitor and evaluate the implementation of AMR policies and regulations.

❖ **We call on youths and youth-led organizations to:**

- Take actions to be responsible for stewards of our environment and health systems, which are directly impacted by AMR.
- Engage and encourage peers and outreach communities including local people, livestock farmers and other relevant people in discussions, workshops, and initiatives that are focusing on AMR that can serve as catalysts for change and raise awareness at the grassroots level.
- Develop new innovative ideas for the establishment of policies for mitigation of AMR issues across the country.
- Involve with peers, stakeholders, national and international organizations to combat AMR to safeguard both animal and public health.

- **FAYI and IAAS both are dedicated to persistently executing strategies to mitigate the problem using One Health approach through:**
- **Youth Symposium on One health and Innovative Idea Sharing Competitions:** We strongly believe that the youths are the future leaders, uniquely positioned to steer our nation towards effective mitigation of the complex and pressing challenges. In order to educate and promote One Health as well as to explore the innovative ideas on policies regarding One Health issues among the students, One Health Think Tank of FAYI, IAAS is strongly committed through the organization of One Health Symposiums for youths in different countries.
- **One Health Awareness Campaigns for Outreach Communities:** The One Health Think Tank of FAYI, IAAS has implemented comprehensive One Health Awareness Campaign Programs for outreach communities designed to engage and educate communities on a wide array of One Health issues. These include antimicrobial resistance, the transmission of zoonotic diseases and strategies for their prevention and control, and so on.
- **One Health Workshops:** We designed One Health Workshops for the students majoring in health sciences for their future stewards, future innovations, advocacy and awareness, policy shaping, community engagement, skill developments and empowerments.
- ✓ **We earnestly urge** a diverse array of youth organizations to establish meaningful connections, while simultaneously extending our call to national and international entities for their invaluable support, encompassing both financial contributions and non-financial assistance, as we collectively endeavor to confront the multifaceted challenges posed by AMR.
- ✓ **FAYI urges** to increase the involvement of youths in One Health approaches adopted by national and international organizations to combat this global issue collectively and effectively.

References

¹O'Neill J. Tackling Drug-resistant Infections Globally: Final Report and Recommendations 2016. UK: HM Government and Wellcome Trust; 2018. Retrieved on 17-05-2020. Available from: <https://amr-review.org/>

- ²Sharma C, Rokana N, Chandra M, Singh BP, Gulhane RD, Gill JP, Ray P, Puniya AK, Panwar H. Antimicrobial resistance: its surveillance, impact, and alternative management strategies in dairy animals. *Frontiers in veterinary science*. 2018 Jan 8;4:237.
- ³Masud AA, Rousham EK, Islam MA, Alam MU, Rahman M, Mamun AA, Sarker S, Asaduzzaman M, Unicomb L. Drivers of antibiotic use in poultry production in Bangladesh: Dependencies and dynamics of a patron-client relationship. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*. 2020 Feb 28;7:78.
- ⁴DGDA. National Drug Policy 2016. Directorate General of Drug Administration. Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh. 2016. Available online: <https://www.dgda.gov.bd/index.php/laws-and-policies/261-national-drug-policy-2016-english-version/file> (accessed on 23 April 2021).
- ⁵Bangladesh Gazette. Fish Feed and Animal Feed Act 2010. Available online: <http://extwprlegs1.fao.org/docs/pdf/bgd165024.pdf> (accessed on 20 April 2021).
- ⁶Chowdhury R, Haque MN, Islam KM, Khaleduzzaman AB. A review on antibiotics in an animal feed. *Bangladesh Journal of Animal Science*. 2009;38(1-2):22-32.

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